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Comparison of different accelerator options for ^{99m}Tc and therapeutic isotope production

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ABSTRACT

Due to shortages in the supply of ^{99m}Tc about 10 years ago and the desire to see an expansion in the use of novel PET, therapeutic and theragnostic radioisotopes, there has been a lot of interest in improving the accelerator production of isotopes by developing new technologies. As the requirements for these stretch the capabilities of existing accelerator technology, ARIES, along with other projects, has been investigating a number of possibilities. These include a compact cyclotron for PET isotope production, linear accelerators and Fixed Field Alternating Gradient accelerators for a variety of radioisotopes and the development of an existing electron accelerator for ^{99m}Tc production. This deliverable will describe the activities being undertaken in ARIES and make a comparison with standard cyclotron production of radioisotopes.

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT ACCELERATOR OPTIONS FOR ^{99m}Tc AND THERAPEUTIC ISOTOPE PRODUCTION

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For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Radioisotopes play a very important role in medicine. They are used both for diagnosis, by providing images using gamma rays produced during their decay, and for treatment by the ionisation the decay products create. Although they have been used for many years and there is a wide range of isotopes potentially available, only a few are actually used in large quantities. These are ^{99m}Tc and ¹⁸F for imaging and ⁹⁰Y and ¹³¹I for therapy. While there are a variety of reasons why this is the case, it is clear that more cost-effective and on-demand production will improve the availability of other promising radioisotopes.

Such production is only available using particle accelerators and, indeed, requires further development of the technology to reduce costs and overcome some technical limitations. In ARIES, a number of new accelerator options are being studied. These include compact systems for the local production of PET isotopes, to enable the use of short-lived isotopes such as ¹¹C and ¹⁵O, various methods for the production of ^{99m}Tc, either directly or via the standard generator method using ⁹⁹Mo, and the production of alpha emitting therapy and theragnostic isotopes, such as ²¹¹At and ²²⁵Ac.

This deliverable reviews the current status of radioisotope production, describes each of the options being studied and shows how these can bring an improvement to the availability of medical radioisotopes.

1. Introduction

Radioisotopes have been used in medicine ever since radioactivity was discovered. Produced in an accelerator or a nuclear reactor, a wide variety of radioisotopes are used for *in-vivo* imaging and therapy for specific diseases. The main applications are:

Imaging

The radioisotope is delivered to the region of the patient to be imaged using a pharmaceutical that has been labelled with a specific radioisotope. The decay products are detected and used to determine the location of each decay event, from which an image can be reconstructed.

The most commonly used imaging technique is single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), in which the radioisotope decays via the emission of a single gamma-ray photon, which is then detected. By far the most commonly used SPECT isotope, and isotope in general, is ^{99m}Tc , which has a half-life of just over 6 hours. It is currently obtained from the decay of ^{99}Mo , which has a half-life of 66 hours, and is produced as a by-product in a nuclear reactor – so-called generator production. Until recently, all ^{99m}Tc was produced in this manner. Initially, this was done in 5 aging test reactors, but in 2008 and 2009 there was a shortage as a result of the two biggest producers being down at the same time. This led to newer reactors being brought online and also to a search for alternative methods of production. There are a number of possible production routes using particle accelerators which are summarised in Figure 1. The timescale for implementation comes from an assessment by the International Atomic Energy Agency in 2013 [1]. The preferred method at that time, and probably still now, was the direct production via $^{100}\text{Mo}(p,2n)^{99m}\text{Tc}$ using high specification cyclotrons. However, it was already clear that newer accelerator designs were required to make the process more cost-effective with respect to reactor production.

The second technique is positron emission tomography (PET), in which the decay results in the emission of a positron. This then annihilates with a nearby electron to release two gamma-rays, which are detected. Although PET is currently not as widely used as SPECT, the emission of two photons means that it tends to have a better image resolution. The dominant PET isotope is ^{18}F , which is usually bound to a glucose analogue, so it is more often taken to sites requiring higher energy, including tumours. The 2 hour half-life makes central production possible. There is, however, a lot of interest in other PET isotopes, in particular ^{11}C , as this can replace ^{12}C in any molecule, so it can be targeted with much better precision. The half-life of ^{11}C is only 20 minutes, making central production almost impossible.

It should be noted that SPECT and PET are very good at identifying the location of tumours, for example, but much worse at showing the surroundings. This is because the radiopharmaceuticals used are designed to deliver them to the highly active tumour cells. To overcome this problem, SPECT and PET are now usually done in combination with another imaging technique such as CT or MRI. These show the surroundings much better, so giving a superior, combined picture of the tumour.

Figure 1: Alternative accelerator production methods for ^{99m}Tc.

Cancer therapy

In this, the radioisotopes used are those that decay into highly-ionising particles – alpha particles (helium nuclei) or high-energy beta particles (electrons) – which are capable of killing cancer cells. They are attached to chemical compounds that are preferentially taken up by cancerous tissue. A promising new therapy involves binding the radioisotope to an antibody that specifically targets a

tumour cell (radio-immunotherapy). This type of therapy has huge potential, but is not being fully exploited currently because most of the radioisotopes used are produced in nuclear reactors, and the supply can be somewhat erratic. Furthermore, although some of the alpha decaying radionuclides with the most potential can be created by accelerators, they require beams of alpha and other accelerated particles for their production. Most of the commercial accelerators are unable to provide these beams.

Targeted alpha Therapy (TAT) is an emerging treatment, which aims at delivering systemic radiation selectively to cancerous cells while minimizing damage to healthy tissues. Its effectiveness is based on the fact that alpha particles (helium nuclei), emitted from radionuclides that decay via an alpha-decay path, release large amounts of energy (of order 100 keV/μm) over very short distances (50–100 μm) causing complex double-stranded DNA breaks, leading to cell death. If the alpha-emitters are concentrated on cancerous cells, toxic effects are confined to cancerous lesions and their surrounding microenvironment. For this reason, TAT is an excellent way to treat diffuse cancers (e.g. leukaemia) or metastasis, providing that an adequate carrier can effectively concentrate the isotope on the cancerous regions [2]. Potential use of TAT for other diseases such as the control of AIDS, microbial, fungal or viral diseases is being investigated.

Alpha-emitting isotopes used so far in pre-clinical and clinical trials are ²²⁵Ac, ²¹¹At, ²¹²Bi, ²¹³Bi, ²¹²Pb, ²²³Ra, and ²²⁷Th. Most of them are products of natural decay chains except for ²¹¹At (Astatine) that can be produced by accelerators in quantities sufficient for clinical trials and treatment. However, its relatively short half-life of 7.2 hours requires the accelerator to be not too far from the clinical setting.

So far, availability of isotopes has been the main limitation to TAT research and adequate schemes for accelerator production and distribution of alpha emitters, in particular of ²¹¹At, are needed to develop TAT beyond the stage of initial clinical trials [3].

Astatine-211 can be produced by collision of an alpha-beam with a natural bismuth target via the ²⁰⁹Bi(α,2n)²¹¹At nuclear reaction. The threshold is at about 20 MeV total energy and peaks at about 31 MeV. An optimum production energy is about 28.5 MeV, which maximizes ²¹¹At yield while minimizing production of ²¹⁰At, problematic because of its 138.4-day half-life alpha emitting daughter, ²¹⁰Po. The cross-section for both reactions is presented in Figure 2.

Astatine-211 decays through a branched pathway, with each decay path producing an alpha particle as it decays to stable lead 207. Figure 3 shows the decay branches. The second branch, involving electron capture decay, leads to the emission of 77-92 keV polonium K X-rays, a valuable means for imaging ²¹¹At distribution (theragnostic) [3]. ²¹¹At is compatible with several carrier molecules allowing targeted delivery.

Figure 2: Cross sections for alpha particle induced reactions on natural Bismuth targets [4]

Figure 3: 211-Astatine decay branches

Another example of a theragnostic isotope is ²²⁵Ac, see Figure 4. This decays by emitting 4 alpha particles and 2 detectable gamma rays. Currently, the main source of this is from reactors, which is limiting its availability. It is possible to make it using accelerators, but via the most common reaction, ²³²Th(p,x)²²⁵Ac, the threshold is above what can be achieved with most commercially available radioisotope cyclotrons, 37 MeV.

Figure 4: The decay chain of ^{225}Ac , from [5]

2. Accelerator production of radioisotopes

Most accelerator-made radioisotopes are created currently in high-intensity cyclotrons using a proton beam over a range of energies from 11 to 30 MeV. Two examples are shown in Figure 5. For SPECT, although almost all ^{99m}Tc production is via reactors, other isotopes such as ^{67}Ga , ^{111}In , ^{123}I and ^{201}Tl are generated using reactions between higher-energy proton beams, accelerated in an accelerator at between 20 and 30 MeV. Currently, however, the production remains low due to the prevalence of ^{99m}Tc and its relatively low production costs.

Figure 5: (Left) 16 MeV cyclotron from GE. (Right) 11 MeV cyclotron from SIEMENS, also showing the radiopharmaceutical production unit.

For PET, almost all the positron-emitters are usually created in reactions involving accelerated protons using accelerators working below 15–20 MeV. This has stimulated the development of small, compact cyclotrons dedicated to the production of the main positron emitters used, ^{18}F , ^{11}C , ^{15}O and

^{13}N . The same accelerators are also useful for production of many of the more novel positron emitters such as ^{64}Cu , ^{86}Y and ^{124}I . Recent developments have included the implementation of very low-energy machines producing for example, ^{18}F in amounts equal to a single patient dose. The short half-life of the most widespread positron emitters, particularly of ^{18}F and ^{11}C , has resulted in the formation of a network of PET production centres in the majority of the developed countries, equipped with cyclotrons with proton-beam energies of between 7 and 19 MeV (about 800 installations worldwide). As a result, the fraction of PET *versus* SPECT imaging has been slowly increasing over the years.

Cyclotrons have also been used to produce several therapeutic radionuclides, although they are mainly at the level of preclinical or early clinical research; they include radionuclides like ^{64}Cu , ^{67}Cu , ^{186}W and ^{211}At . Finally, cyclotrons provide several important parent radioisotopes in the manufacturing of radioisotope generators – the isotopes from which the clinically active isotopes are generated by radioactive decay. For example, ^{68}Ga is created through the decay of ^{68}Ge , where ^{68}Ga is one of the novel positron emitters that is already established in clinical practice.

3. New accelerator technologies for radioisotope production under development

For the production of novel and more sophisticated radioisotopes and, indeed, more cost-effective production of those already in use, the economics or even the technical feasibility of a particular radioisotope production, is determined by two parameters closely related to accelerator technology – the maximum available beam energy and the maximum available current. In some cases, the availability of beams for particles other than protons, like deuterons or alpha particles, is also a key factor in production of a particular radioisotope (for example, ^{211}At can be efficiently obtained only with use of an alpha-particle beam).

The modern and efficient production of medical radioisotopes thus requires accelerators that are:

- » versatile – able to be tuned over a wide energy range to high energies (30 MeV) to produce a wider range of isotopes;
- » relatively inexpensive to acquire and cost-effective to run;
- » capable of running at high currents to increase yields.

In ARIES, five types of accelerator are being studied to bring improvements in radioisotope production over the existing cyclotrons and to meet these requirements. These are:

- (1) A very compact cyclotron for the production of PET isotopes, AMIT
- (2) The use of an existing “Rhodotron” accelerator to make ^{99m}Tc , which is being studied by IBA
- (3) The development of an existing linear accelerator by a consortium led by ASML, a Dutch manufacturer of lithographic machines for the semi-conductor industry, and including the ARIES partner RI, to produce ^{99m}Tc
- (4) A new Fixed Field Alternating Gradient accelerator being studied by HUD
- (5) A compact linear accelerator being studied by CERN.

These are considered in the following sub-sections.

3.1 AMIT CYCLOTRON

AMIT cyclotron for ^{18}F and ^{11}C production, developed by CIEMAT, represents a really innovative solution for compact and efficient superconducting magnets for radioisotope production. The design has been strongly determined by the requirement of its installation in a non-dedicated facility, for example a hospital, imposing specifications in terms of limited power supply, refrigeration demands, operational risks and environmental effects [6]. The aim is to create single patient doses of, in particular, the short-lived ^{11}C isotope, close to the patient so it can be used before too much has decayed away. The cyclotron is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: An engineering drawing of the AMIT cyclotron

The most important features are the weak focusing configuration, a 4 T superconducting magnet, high accelerating gradient and internal PIG H-ion source. The superconducting magnet has been designed to achieve a stable operation, providing a good magnetic field quality imposed by beam dynamics simulations, as well minimum thermal losses for superconducting operation. To provide a system as autonomous as possible, additional supplies have to be reduced as much as possible so that operational costs are minimized. The use of a large liquefaction cryogenic facility is discarded for cyclotrons devoted to on-demand radiopharmaceutical productions. Additionally, bath-type cooling refrigeration of the superconducting magnet of such compact cyclotrons would result in additional operational costs, given the need of periodic refill of cryogen by skilled technicians. For an autonomous, cheap and compact radioisotope production facility, the AMIT cyclotron uses a flow refrigeration scheme in a closed cycle. A forced internal flow of two-phase helium will be in direct contact with the coils, being more effective. An autonomous liquefaction system for producing this liquid helium, named Cryogenic Supply System (CSS) was developed in collaboration with CERN.

The CSS is an assembly of heat exchangers, heaters and temperature sensors that receives two inlets of helium gas (ambient temperature and cold gases). It cools them down to first and second stage temperatures, respectively. Once the steady state is reached, the latter will become liquid helium. It includes one cryocooler for liquefaction, being compatible with the main objective of a compact and low cost facility. A low-loss helium transfer line links the CSS with the magnet cryostat for remote cooling, entering in the cyclotron connection box. Figure 7 shows the cooling system being tested and Table 1 has a comparison between many radioisotope producing cyclotrons, including AMIT.

Figure 7: Testing of the AMIT cryogenic system.

Table 1: A selection of the commercially available radioisotope production cyclotrons, separated into low (<15 MeV), medium (15-30 MeV) and high energy (>30 MeV), showing a comparison with AMIT

Cyclotron	Ep (MeV)	Ip (μA)	Peak B (T)	Weight (Tons)
LOW ENERGY				
<i>GENtrace, GE [7]</i>	7.8	-	2.2	6.7
<i>MINItrace, GE [7]</i>	9.6	>50	2.2	9.1
<i>Eclipse, Siemens [8]</i>	11	>120	1.9	11
<i>Cyclone10, IBA [9]</i>	10	>150	1.9	12
<i>Cyclone11, IBA [10]</i>	11	120	1.9	13
<i>TR14, ACSI [11]</i>	14	>100	2.1	23
<i>BG-75, ABT [12]</i>	7.5	5	1.8	3.2
<i>AMIT, CIEMAT [13]</i>	8.5	>10	4	2.5
<i>ION12SC, Ionetix [14]</i>	12	~10	4.5	2

<i>iMITRACE, PMB-ALCEN[15]</i>	12	50	2.3	4.5
MEDIUM ENERGY				
<i>BEST15, BEST[16]</i>	15	400	-	14 (magnet)
<i>PETTrace ,GE [7]</i>	16.5	>100	1.9	22
<i>Cyclone18 IBA [17]</i>	18	150	1.9	25
<i>KIUBE, IBA [18]</i>	18	<300	-	18
<i>TR19, ACSI [11]</i>	19	>300	2.1	22
<i>TR24, ACSI [11]</i>	24	>300	2.1	84
<i>BEST25, BEST [16]</i>	25	400	-	50 (magnet)
<i>Cyclone30,IBA [19]</i>	30	<1500	1.7	50
<i>TR30, ACSI [20]</i>	30	>1000	1.9	56
HIGH ENERGY				
<i>BEST35, BEST [16]</i>	35	1000	-	55 (magnet)
<i>Cyclone70, IBA [21]</i>	70	<750	1.6	145
<i>BEST70, BEST [22]</i>	70	700	1.6	195 (magnet)

3.2. ELECTRON RHODOTRON

The standard cyclotron production method for ^{99m}Tc is through the direct reaction ¹⁰⁰Mo(p,2n)^{99m}Tc. This is used because it has a significantly higher yield than the production of ⁹⁹Mo first. However, the fact that is not a direct replacement of the existing generator method and the ^{99m}Tc lifetime is only 6 hours makes it more complicated for the suppliers of radiopharmaceuticals.

As a result, an alternative production method has been studied and implemented by IBA, based on studies done elsewhere [23]. This is to use photo-production via the reaction ¹⁰⁰Mo(γ,n)⁹⁹Mo. A new version of an existing high beam current accelerator, called the Rhodotron, is used [24]. Typically, these accelerate the beam to 10 MeV, but the new version, the TT300-HE, is capable of producing 125 kW of electrons at 40 MeV (see Figure 8).

The isotope production proceeds by using a heavy metal converter, such as tungsten or tantalum, immediately in front of an enriched ¹⁰⁰Mo target, to around 95%. The converter produces the gamma rays required for the reaction. A comparison between this technique and other production methods is shown in Table 2. To set the scale, the current world-wide demand for ⁹⁹Mo is around 70k Ci week. The “6-day Ci” value is the activity left after 6 days, to allow for production and distribution and shows that the

Rhodotron option can produce about 125 Ci per week, meaning that around 560 would be required for the entire world's supply. Although this number is large, it is highly competitive with the other viable options.

Following trials of this technique, North Star Medical has signed a contract for 8 such devices, with down payments made on the first two. These are due to be operational in 2021 and provide a non-uranium based source of ^{99m}Mo for the US.

Figure 8: Drawing of the IBA TT300-HE Rhodotron.

Table 2: A comparison between accelerator methods for ^{99m}Mo production, from [25]. ADSR is an Accelerator Driven Sub-critical Reactor [26] and LEU is a Low Enriched Uranium target.

Particle	Accelerator	Reaction	Energy	Beam power	Target	6-day-Ci/wk
Proton [27]	ADSR	²³⁵ U(n,fission) ^{99m} Mo	1 GeV	1 MW	LEU	~6000
Proton [27]	ADSR	⁹⁸ Mo(n,γ) ^{99m} Mo	1 GeV	1 MW	⁹⁸ Mo	~3000
Proton [28]	ADSR	²³⁵ U(n,fission) ^{99m} Mo	200 MeV	100 kW	LEU	~7000
Electron [23]	RF Linac	²³⁸ U(γ,fission) ^{99m} Mo	50 MeV	1 MW	Natural U	~180
Electron [23]	RF Linac	¹⁰⁰ Mo(γ,n) ^{99m} Mo	>30 MeV	500 kW	¹⁰⁰ Mo	~500

Electron [29]	RF Linac	¹⁰⁰ Mo(γ,n) ⁹⁹ Mo	25 MeV	20 kW	Natural Mo	~5
Electron [24]	Rhodotron	¹⁰⁰ Mo(γ,n) ⁹⁹ Mo	40 MeV	125 kW	¹⁰⁰ Mo	~125
Proton [30]	Cyclotron	¹⁰⁰ Mo(p,pn) ⁹⁹ Mo	45 MeV	4.5 kW	¹⁰⁰ Mo	~2.5
Proton [30]	Cyclotron	¹⁰⁰ Mo(p,pn) ⁹⁹ Mo	45 MeV	4.5 kW	Natural Mo	~0.25

3.3 SUPERCONDUCTING ELECTRON LINEAR ACCELERATOR

ASML, Institute for Radioelements (IRE), Research Instruments and partners have designed and are constructing an alternative type of accelerator for the photo-production of ⁹⁹Mo. This is a 60 MeV superconducting electron linear accelerator based on ASML’s design for an extreme ultra-violet free electron laser (see Figure 9). The project is called Lighthouse. The accelerator plus target and processing chamber are 52 m long by 10 m wide at the widest point.

Figure 9: The layout of the Lighthouse facility for the photo-production on ⁹⁹Mo. The laser injector is at the left hand end. The beam is accelerated along the linac before being split into two to hit both sides of the enriched ¹⁰⁰Mo target. The processing chamber is on the right of the picture.

The linac employs a laser electron source capable of producing a 30 mA beam. This is accelerated through five 8-cell cavities before a “kicker” beam splitter splits the beam and transport arcs deliver the beam to both sides of the target. A system has also been designed to extract the target and move it to the processing chamber (see Figure 10). Simulations suggest that after the processing, Lighthouse will be able to produce more than 3800 6-day-Ci per week, making it a highly competitive option.

The facility has been designed and is currently under construction. It is expected to be ready for commissioning in 2023 with commercial production beginning at the start of 2025.

Figure 10: Lighthouse target region and processing chamber

3.4 FIXED FIELD ALTERNATING GRADIENT ACCELERATOR

Although the first FFAG designs were developed in the 1950's [31] it is only recently that their potential is beginning to be realised. The difficulties in the design and manufacturing of complex magnetic fields, that held back early development, have been overcome with modern computer aided design and manufacturing techniques. This has opened up a new era of interest in FFAGs and designs have been made for a range of applications.

For radioisotope production, high currents and stable, reliable operation are needed to produce large enough yields to make production commercially viable. FFAGs are well suited for this as they have large dynamic apertures and so can handle the emittance growth from space charge effects resulting from large current operation.

In ARIES, the design of a compact non-linear non-scaling FFAG has been undertaken for the production of ^{99m}Tc and ^{211}At for SPECT imaging and radiotherapy with alpha particles, respectively [32]. ^{99m}Tc requires 14-20 MeV protons while ^{211}At needs 28 MeV alpha particles. As such the energy range of the machine is from 75keV to 28 MeV and the use of both protons and alpha particles has been investigated.

The basic design consists of four separate radial sector magnets and two single gap RF cavities (see Figure 11). The magnetic field variation as a function of radius is defined by a polynomial expansion up to sextupole and is optimised with an edge angle to maintain sufficient isochronicity and to stabilise the tunes.

Figure 11: General layout of the FFAG, with the magnets shown in red and the RF cavities in green. Two sectors are left open for injection and extraction.

3.4.1 Simulations

Simulations have been carried out using the OPAL code [33] to characterise the machine's performance. For protons, the maximum time of flight variation across the energy range is $\pm 0.15\%$ and the integrated variation is 0.632% (see Figure 12). As demonstrated by the EMMA FFAG [34], this is sufficiently isochronous to allow for fixed frequency RF and CW operation. The betatron tunes are shown in Figure 13. These are stable at median to high energy with just a small increase in the horizontal tune and no resonances (up to 3rd order) crossed. At low energy, the fringe fields begin to overlap causing a depression of the vertical tune which results in the crossing of several resonances including an integer resonance. However, all the resonances are crossed quickly and tracking with Opal suggests these are not a problem. The dynamic apertures were found to be large, peaking at around 12.5 MeV in the horizontal plane with 150π m mrad and at 24 MeV in the vertical at 41.4π m mrad.

Figure 12: Time of flight variation from 75 keV to 28 MeV.

Figure 13: Tune variations from 75 keV to 28 MeV, using Opal, COSY and pyZgoubi.

Investigation of the RF phase space has shown that an acceleration channel to 28 MeV opens up at 20 kV/turn acceleration when using the 1st harmonic. This, however, corresponds to a frequency of 7.5 MHz and a very large cavity. With a 100 kV/turn, acceleration is achievable up to the 5th harmonic, so a much higher frequency and smaller cavity. There is significant coupling from the longitudinal to transverse planes due to the effect of the longitudinal emittance on the energy spread

of the beam. The accelerating voltage also affects the energy spread of the beam as well as the crossing rate of any resonances. Consequently increasing voltages results in lower emittances.

Simulation of alpha particles using the same magnetic field reveals that tunes and dynamic apertures are very similar to those of protons. The RF phase space, however, is significantly more restricted. Only the 1st harmonic is usable unless very large accelerating gradients are used. The emittances are significantly larger than for protons, due largely to the greater phase slip and resulting increased energy spread of the beam. However, by optimising the magnetic field for alpha particles, operation at the 8th harmonic is easily achievable, with 100° phase acceptance.

An investigation of the effect of magnetic field errors on the dynamic aperture of the machine shows that it is quite resistant to them, requiring large field errors, around 5%, before a significant reduction in the dynamic aperture is observed.

Simulation of space charge effects revealed that the design is capable of accelerating high currents for both protons and alpha particles. Protons can be accelerated with up to 4mA beam current with no losses and at 20mA with 2.3% beam losses. Alpha particles can be accelerated with minimal losses up to 800μA. For protons it was found that using the 2nd or 3rd harmonic gave the best results under high current conditions. The design compares well with currently available commercial cyclotrons which are capable of delivering 400μA to 1.2 mA of beam current for protons, and up to 50μAe for alpha particles.

3.4.2 Injection and extraction

Radial injection has been studied, along a radius between two magnets, so that the magnetic field is very small, except towards the centre of the machine. As the momentum is small, the beam is actually straight-forward to capture under these circumstances.

The baseline design for the FFAG assumes the beam will be extracted and used on an external target. The preferred extraction method is an electrostatic deflector followed by a septum, as employed at PSI [35]. This requires a sufficient separation between the last two orbits in the accelerator, particularly at high beam current. This separation is shown in Figure 14a for the design extended to 35 MeV. The overlap is clearly too large. One method of improving the orbit separation is to induce a coherent oscillation of the bunch around the accelerated orbit [36]. Figure 14b shows the final two turns under the same conditions as in Figure 14a but with a coherent oscillation induced by displacing the beam at injection. The intensity between orbits now drops to < 5 % of the peak. This improved separation allows for a much cleaner extraction, especially if combined with a collimation set up to reduce the size of the beam halo and tail.

(a) No coherent oscillations.

(b) With coherent oscillations.

Figure 14: Separation between the last two orbits in a 35 MeV version of the FFAG, without (a) and with (b) coherent oscillations in the orbits introduced.

As another alternative, an internal target and recycled beam has been investigated to see if it could improve ^{99m}Tc yield compared to using a thick external target. The idea is to use a thin target, to reduce beam blow up and loss, and to pass the beam through it multiple times to increase the yield. The energy lost is then restored by the cavity following the target.

Simulations show that when using a 0.005 mm thick ¹⁰⁰Mo target, the beam intensity is reduced by 50% in 35 turns, which is too small. The main limitation is the vertical aperture of ± 20 mm, which has a significant impact on the beam survival. Increasing this by ± 10 mm almost doubles the beam survival time. The other main influence on beam survival comes from minimising the longitudinal emittance growth in the target. Two techniques were studied to reduce this: a wedge shaped target and an additional RF cavity placed at the target radius. The wedge shaped target improved beam survival by 20% and the RF stabilisation improved it by 50%. When both techniques are implemented simultaneously the effect was amplified and an improvement of 140% was observed. With these improvements a theoretical yield of up to 18 GBq/ μ A could be achieved. This would represent a significant improvement on the thick target yield of up to 5 GBq/ μ A. Clearly, however, careful design of the target area will be necessary to avoid radiation damage to the sensitive components of machine, cooling and the extraction and replacement of the target.

Although the work done so far has demonstrated that this FFAG has significant potential to bring improvements over the cyclotrons currently in use for ^{99m}Tc and therapy isotope production, much further work is still required. In particular, an engineering design of the main machine components and the machine itself and prototyping of the magnets.

3.5. ION LINEAR ACCELERATOR

Ion linear accelerators (linacs) can be a valid alternative to low-energy cyclotrons for the production of isotopes for PET and for therapy. As compared to cyclotrons, linacs have much lower beam loss and their limited dimensions, weight, and required shielding make it possible to install the accelerator in the hospital.

New perspectives for isotope production with linacs have been opened up by the recent development at CERN of a compact Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ), operating at high frequency [37]. The RFQ is the first fundamental accelerator element following the ion source. In its original version (Figure 15) this new RFQ has been configured as a 2-meter-long 5 MeV injector for a proton therapy linac being built by the ADAM/AVO company [38]. The high operation frequency allows smaller dimensions and lower construction costs as compared to other RFQ designs. The RFQ is designed to be modular, made of 0.5 m long elements mechanically coupled.

Figure 15: The 2-m RFQ for ADAM/AVO, installed in the CERN test stand

3.5.1 Linac for Targeted Alpha Therapy

The relatively low production energy and short half-life make At-211 an ideal therapeutic isotope to be produced by a compact linear accelerator. Very few cyclotrons exist that are optimised to produce high intensities of alpha particles, in particular because of limitations related to the high extraction losses.

The linear accelerator for TAT production can make use of a new beam optics design for the 750 MHz RFQ, recently developed to accelerate fully-stripped Carbon ions (charge-to-mass ratio 0.5) to an energy of 5 MeV/u in the front-end of a Carbon-ion linac for particle therapy [39]. The same design can be used to accelerate alpha particles, which have identical charge-to-mass ratio, in a linac devoted to Astatine production.

Because the RFQ becomes very inefficient at high energy, to reach the ²¹¹At production energy it must be followed by another accelerating section, possibly at the same frequency. A structure presently under development at CERN, the 750 MHz Quasi-Alvarez (QA) Drift-Tube Linac, can be used to effectively accelerate between the RFQ and the ²¹¹At production target.

This particular type of accelerating structure was originally designed for efficient heavy-ion acceleration at high-frequency with good control of beam optics parameters [40, 41]. It consists of a Drift-Tube Linac where only one drift tube out of three contains a quadrupole (Figure 16). The distance between gaps is $\beta\lambda$ (with β the relativistic velocity and λ the wavelength) around short drift tubes as usual in DTLs, while it is increased to $2\beta\lambda$ around the large drift tube containing the quadrupole. The drift tube diameter of 15.5 mm is sufficient to house a permanent quadrupole and the cooling channel required for operation at 10% duty cycle. A map of the electric field in a QA tank going from 5 to 7 MeV/u is presented in Figure 17 [42].

Figure 16: 3D simulation of a Quasi-Alvarez tank

Figure 17: Electric field map in the QA tank 5-7 MeV/u

A scheme of the TAT production accelerator using RFQ and QA is shown in Figure 18, and its key parameters are presented in Table 3. A commercial ECR source for alpha-particles produces a current of 0.5 mA that is then accelerated by the 750-MHz Radio-Frequency Quadrupole up to 5 MeV/u (20

MeV total energy). The RFQ is optimised for minimum length and RF power with a resulting beam transmission of 50%. The RFQ is followed by a Quasi-Alvarez tank made of 27 cells and operating at an average accelerating field of 4 MV/m. The latter brings the energy to 7 MeV/u (28 MeV total). The accelerator operates at 10% duty cycle, producing an average current of 20 μ A. Its total length, taking into account the ion source and the locally shielded production target, should not exceed 10 metres. The overall RF power is 771 kW, to be provided by eight solid-state amplifier units at 100 kW each. Assuming a 50% amplifier efficiency, the total mains power is about 160 kW.

Figure 18: scheme of the Astatine production system

Table 3: Alpha accelerator parameters

	RFQ	Quasi-Alvarez	
Frequency	750	750	MHz
Input energy	0.015	5.06	MeV/u
Output energy	5.06	7	MeV/u
Length	4.8	1.6	m
Peak output current	200	200	μ A
Average current	20	20	μ A
Beam duty cycle	10	10	%
Peak RF power	600	171	kW

The ²¹¹At production yield numerically calculated for 28 MeV energy on target and 20 μ A current, after a saturation time of $3.5 T_{1/2} \cong 24$ hours, is 10.4 GBq [43]. Production yield values reported in literature for real cases where evaporation loss of ²¹¹At is present are only slightly lower, 400 MBq/ μ A corresponding to 8 GBq for 20 μ A. [4]. Improved target cooling, geometry and materials might mitigate evaporation loss [4, 44].

Data available in literature allow the calculation of the equivalent doses required for treatment [45]. Neglecting the loss of activity during transport, this accelerator configuration would be adequate for producing between 100 and 500 doses for post-surgery treatment of ovarian cancer, where the dose per patient was between 20 and 100 MBq, and for producing between 30 and 150 doses in the case of post-surgery brain tumour therapy, where the administered dose per patient was between 70 and 350 MBq.

3.5.2 Linac for PET

For imaging, the PET isotope production energy can be reached by a single RFQ, made of a sequence of 0.5 m units. A design has been developed at CERN, where the beam optics defined by the modulation of the RFQ electrodes is such that all particle loss occurs at energies lower than 1 MeV, below the activation threshold. This ensures that no beam loss will activate the accelerator and that the entire beam accelerated to high energy will go to the target, which is contained in a shielded enclosure. The radio pharmacy unit can be placed directly on the target enclosure. The overall layout of the system is shown in Figure 19. Here the ion source is on the left, the shielded target enclosure on the right, and the cables from the RFQ connect to the Radio-Frequency amplifiers located in an adjacent room.

Figure 19: RFQ-based PET isotope production system.

A calculation of target shielding was made for the case of 10 MeV proton energy assuming as maximum dose on the outside of the enclosure the value of 2 μ Sv/h that corresponds in most legislations to a radiation-controlled area accessible at any time to personnel wearing a radiation dosimeter. Different configurations based on successive layers of iron, polyethylene and borated (5%) polyethylene were compared using the FLUKA code and progressively optimised for minimum overall thickness using genetic algorithms. The calculation indicates that a shielding with a total radius of 1 m can reduce the dose at contact during operation at the required value [46]. Further optimisation of the shielding is possible and will be done at a further stage.

While an initial PET isotopes production system was designed for 10 MeV proton energy [49], a recent cost analysis [50] indicated that, the construction cost of a linac being roughly proportional to its energy, the economic optimum for production of both ¹⁸F and ¹¹C lies between the two peaks of

Figures 20 and 21, at about 6.5 MeV. A scheme of a corresponding optimised 6.5 MeV isotope production unit is presented in Figure 22.

Figure 20: Excitation function of the reaction $^{18}\text{O}(p,n)^{18}\text{F}$ [47].

Figure 21: Excitation function of $^{14}\text{N}(p,\alpha)^{11}\text{C}$ reaction [48].

Figure 22: Scheme of the 6.5 MeV RFQ-based PET isotope production system.

The 2.5 m long RFQ is composed of five 0.5 m modules, each fed by a 100 kW solid-state amplifier at 750 MHz. Solid-state Radio-Frequency technology is now mature enough to allow reaching powers in the 100 kW range, providing extreme reliability thanks to redundant amplifier modules, for a lower cost with respect to other amplifier configurations. The accelerator modules are water-cooled, the cooling circuit being connected to an external heat exchanger. This system will operate at 10% duty cycle, with a peak proton current of 300 μ A generating 30 μ A of average beam power on the target. This system weighs less than 5 tons for a floor space of less than 10 m², most of the weight being related to the local target shielding of radius < 1 m. This value is however pessimistic because the target shielding calculations were not repeated for 6.5 MeV - the shielding thickness is expected to be considerably lower at this energy than for 10 MeV. The power from the mains is about 30 kVA. The parameters of this accelerator system are reported in Table 4. It has been estimated that the 6.5 MeV isotope production system can be produced and commercialised at a 20% lower cost than equivalent cyclotron-based systems [50]. Additional savings would come from the reduced maintenance costs with respect to a cyclotron system.

Table 4: Parameters of the 6.5 MeV RFQ system for PET isotopes production.

Input / Output Energy	20 keV / 7 MeV
Accelerator length	2.5 m
Operating Frequency	750 MHz
Output peak current	300 μ A
Duty cycle	10 %
Beam pulse repetition frequency	200 Hz
Beam pulse length	500 μ s
Output average current	30 μ A
RF Power, peak	400 kW
RF Power, average	<30 kW
Surface (accelerator, source, target)	10 m ²
Surface (RF and equipment room)	10 m ²
Total weight of accelerator	350 kg
Total system weight	<5 tons
Mains power	35 kVA

The target system could house two interchangeable targets for the production of the two most common PET isotopes, ¹⁸F and ¹¹C.

The ¹⁸F production yield, estimated from numerical calculations assuming a proton beam of 10 MeV energy on target and 1 μ A current, after a saturation time of 3.5 T_{1/2} \cong 6.4 hours, is 5.22 GBq/ μ A [51]

in good agreement with literature [53]. The saturation yield produced for a lower energy of 7 MeV is 2.71 GBq/μA, about 50% lower. The ¹⁸F saturation yields and the corresponding number of PET doses for different beam energies (from 3 to 15 MeV and 1 μA current) are reported in Table 5. Here is considered an average dose of ¹⁸F- FDG of about 10 mCi for a patient of 80kg based on literature data [52] and routine experience of a hospital [51]. For a linac system of 10 MeV energy, 20 μA current and 6.4 hours irradiation the saturation yield is about 104.4 GBq (282 doses), while for 6.5 MeV the saturation yield is 2.47 GBq/μA, resulting for 30 μA beam current in 74,1 GBq, which is equivalent to 200 doses.

Data received from a typical medium-size hospital [51] supplied twice per day by a production facility requiring five and a half hours for delivery, by car and airplane, indicate that for a typical routine of 12 patients per day the produced yield at the facility is approximately 120 GBq, out of which only 15 GBq reach the hospital, and 4.4 GBq are actually used throughout the day. This could be avoided with a local production unit. A linac system at 6.5 MeV energy only delivering a current of 20-30 μA can easily cover the needs of much larger hospitals.

Table 5: Saturation yields of produced ¹⁸F for different proton beam energies, for 1 μA current, and equivalent number of doses for PET diagnosis [51].

Beam energy (MeV)	Sat. Yield GBq/1 μA	PET doses
3	0,05	0,1
4	0,28	0,8
5	0,93	2,5
6	1,92	5,2
7	2,71	7,3
8	3,64	9,8
9	4,59	12,4
10	5,22	14,1
11	6,09	16,5
12	6,64	17,9
13	7,25	19,6
14	7,81	21,1
15	8,24	22,3

The ¹¹C production yield calculated numerically assuming a proton beam of 10 MeV energy on target and 1 μA current, after a saturation time of 3.5 T_{1/2} ≅ 1.2 hours, is 2.63 GBq/μA [51], again very similar to cases reported in literature [53]. An average dose of ¹¹C (Choline) is around 370-740 MBq, equivalent to 10-20 mCi [54,55]. For an energy of 10 MeV, 20 μA and irradiation time of 3.5T_{1/2}, the saturation yield is 52.6 GBq. Assuming a 10-20 mCi ¹¹C average dose per patient, this produced yield will provide for 71-142 doses in 1.2 h.

Positron-emitting isotopes that could be candidates to be produced by a low-energy RFQ-based linac are ¹⁸F (3-18 MeV), ¹¹C (3-13 MeV), ¹³N (7-16 MeV), ¹⁵O (0-10 MeV) and ⁴⁴Sc (9-10 MeV). Their saturation yields (for 10 MeV, 1 μA) together with their properties are summarised in Table 6.

Table 6: PET radioisotopes with low production energy: characteristics and saturation yields.

Nuclide	T _{1/2} [min]	Mode of decay	Production route	Yield at saturation time for energy of 10 MeV [GBq/μA]
¹¹ C	20.4	β ⁺ (99.8%), EC (0.2%)	¹⁴ N(p,α) ¹¹ C	2.71 [Ref.51]
¹³ N	9.97	β ⁺ (100)	¹⁶ O(p,α) ¹³ N	0.63 [Ref.56]
¹⁵ O	2	β ⁺ (99.9%), EC (0.1%)	¹⁵ N(p,n) ¹⁵ O	2.39 [Ref.46]
¹⁸ F	109.8	β ⁺ (97%), EC (3%)	¹⁸ O(p,n) ¹⁸ F	5.22 [Ref.51]
⁴⁴ Sc	238	β ⁺ (94.3%) EC (5.7%)	⁴⁴ Ca(p,n) ⁴⁴ Sc	4.49 [Ref.57]

4. Conclusions

Radioisotopes have been employed in medicine ever since radioactivity was discovered. Their main uses are in imaging and therapy and a wide range of different isotopes are potentially available, bringing many different advantages. Currently, however, only a very limited number are being used and the potential is not being fully exploited.

Particle accelerators can significantly improve the availability of many radioisotopes and also alleviate concerns about the future availability of the most commonly used isotope, ^{99m}Tc. However, the accelerators themselves need further development to improve their cost-effectiveness compared to reactor production and their flexibility to enable on-demand production.

A number of accelerator options are being studied by partners and associate partners in ARIES. These include:

- (1) A very compact cyclotron for the production of PET isotopes, AMIT, from CIEMAT. This will enable the production of patient-sized doses of a variety of PET isotopes close the patients being imaged, making more available for use and likely reducing the cost of production.
- (2) The use of an existing “Rhodotron” accelerator to make ^{99m}Tc , which is being studied by IBA. This is now looking to be a very competitive method for production and is likely to reduce the need for reactor production,
- (3) The development of an existing electron linear accelerator by a consortium led by ASML and IRE to produce ^{99m}Tc . This is an alternative to (2), but with a longer timescale.
- (4) A new Fixed Field Alternating Gradient accelerator being studied by HUD. This can be used for ^{99m}Tc and ^{211}At and looks very competitive with cyclotron production. However, further engineering and prototyping work is still required.
- (5) An ion linear accelerator being studied by CERN, in particular for ^{211}At production, but also with the capability of hospital production of PET isotopes.

All of these bring potential improvements over the cyclotrons that are currently used for almost all accelerator radioisotope production and could help to expand the use of radioisotopes in Europe and further afield. The work on (1), (2) and (5) is advanced and these can or could be in use over the next year or two.

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